

THE ATTACHMENT OF TENDON TO BONE: STRATEGIES FOR MECHANICALLY ROBUST CONNECTIONS BETWEEN DISSIMILAR MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

The attachment of dissimilar materials is a major challenge because of the high levels of localized stress that develop at such interfaces. An effective biologic solution to this problem can be seen at the attachment of tendon (a compliant, structural “soft tissue”) to bone (a stiff, structural “hard tissue”). The enthesis, a transitional tissue that exists between uninjured tendon and bone, is not recreated during healing, so surgical reattachment of these two dissimilar biologic materials often fails (e.g., recurrent tears after rotator cuff repair are as high as 94%). To develop successful strategies for tissue engineering at the enthesis, we must first understand the mechanisms by which the natural attachment transfers load between tendon and bone, and how cells build a functional attachment during development. In order to achieve these goals, we are focusing on defining the design criteria using structure-function biomechanical studies, defining the roadmap using developmental biology, understanding the healing process using animal models, and engineering new biomaterials using regenerative medicine approaches.

1 INTRODUCTION

Connective tissue injuries occurring at or near the interface between soft tissue and bone commonly result in pain, disability and significant medical costs [1]. Tears of the rotator cuff tendons of the shoulder and cruciate ligaments of the knee, for example, normally require surgical attachment of a tendon to its bony insertion. Surgical attachment of torn rotator cuff tendon(s) to their bony insertion(s) is the most common shoulder procedure and a well-known clinical challenge, with failure rates ranging from 20% for repair of small tears to 94% for repair of massive tears [2, 3]. In the lower extremity, the most commonly injured ligament is the anterior cruciate ligament (ACL), resulting in approximately 100,000 ACL reconstructions in the US each year [4]. Injury to the ACL reduces knee stability and predisposes the patient to osteoarthritis later in life [5]. Poor tendon-to-bone healing after reconstruction can lead to graft slippage between the graft and bone tunnel, resulting in joint laxity and subsequent instability [6].

Uninjured insertions possess a transitional region between soft tissue and bone that exhibits gradations in cell phenotype, tissue organization, tissue composition, and tissue mechanical properties (Figure 1). The gradations facilitate the effective transfer of load between two materials with vastly different mechanical properties (soft, compliant tendon/ligament to hard, stiff bone) by reducing the potentially damaging stress concentrations that would otherwise arise at the interface [7-10]. Following surgical or natural repair processes, this transitional region is not regenerated [11-14]. This exposes the insertion to high stresses and an increased risk for failure. As a result, current surgical repair techniques have high re-injury rates. Understanding the structural changes that lead to injury and developing strategies to reduce these surgical failure rates will have a major impact in improving joint function in these patients.

Tendon (composed primarily of type I collagen) and bone (composed of type I collagen and a stiff, carbonated hydroxylapatite referred to here as “mineral”) are hierarchical materials from the nanometer to millimeter scales. In tendon, triple-helix type I collagen molecules (300 nm length, 1.5 nm diameter) pack together to form microfibrils [15, 16]. Microfibrils are typically defined as five collagen molecules stacked in a quarter-stagger array [17, 18]. The collagen is stacked with a 36 nm gap between the *N*- terminus of one collagen molecule and the *C*- terminus of the succeeding molecule. The collagen molecules are staggered relative to each other by 67 nm. Neighboring microfibrils interdigitate, imposing order upon a mildly twisted lattice that forms the next level structure termed a fibril (50-200 nm in diameter). At the next level of structural hierarchy, fibrils close-pack into larger structures to form fibers (3-7 μm in diameter). The fibers then combine to form fascicles (diameters on the order of micrometers), and at this level a characteristic “crimp” pattern can be seen histologically [16, 19]. Finally, fascicles are bundled together through a fascicular membrane to form tendon (with a diameter on the order of millimeters or centimeters). Mineral platelets accumulate on this collagen-based template in gap channels, in the intrafibrillar spaces, and on fibril surfaces to form mineralized tissues [20-23]. At the interface between unmineralized tendon and mineralized bone, a spatial gradation exists in mineral content [24].

The solution to improved tendon-to-bone healing may lie in tissue engineering strategies [25, 26]. Fabrication of a biomimetic material that recreates the functional gradients seen at the natural, uninjured, tendon-to-bone attachment will have significant impact on rotator cuff repair and ACL reconstruction. However, such scaffolds cannot be synthesized successfully without an understanding of mechanism of load transfer at the health tendon-to-bone attachment. Specifically, a better understanding is needed of the toughening and strengthening mechanisms by which the two dissimilar materials, tendon and bone, attach effectively. Previous research in bone and tendon has demonstrated that such mechanisms exist at multiple length scales [9, 27-32]. Therefore, the tendon-to-bone attachment must be studied across hierarchical levels and links must be developed across these hierarchies.

Figure 1: Tendons attach to bone across a functionally graded fibrocartilaginous transition site (left: toluidine blue-stained section from an adult rat supraspinatus tendon-to-bone insertion).

2 DEVELOPING STRATEGIES FOR ROBUST TENDON-TO-BONE ATTACHMENT

2.1 Structure-function relationships - Defining the design criteria

We have demonstrated that the enthesis is a functionally graded material with regard to its composition, structural organization, and mechanical properties [8, 9, 33-36]. A number of mechanisms across multiple spatial scales results in a robust mechanical attachment between the two

materials, including: nanometer scale accumulation of mineral crystals on collagen fibrils, micrometer scale roughness resulting in interdigitation, and millimeter scale changes to the attachment footprint area to normalize stress (Figure 2). Understanding these mechanisms of load transfer provides the design criteria for effective attachment of tendon to bone.

Figure 2: At the millimeter length scale (left), tendon attaches to bone over a large footprint area. At the micrometer length scale (middle), gradients exist in mineral content and orientation, and tissues interdigitate across wavy interfaces. At the nanometer length scale (right), mineral accumulates on collagen fibril gap spaces and surfaces to stiffen the fibrils.

2.2 Developmental biology – Defining the roadmap

The enthesis mineralizes and matures postnatally through a coordinated set of biologic events driven by mechanical loading and genetic cues [37-41]. We have studied the role of muscle loading on enthesis development by paralyzing the rotator cuff muscles at birth in mice. Furthermore, we have identified a unique population of hedgehog-positive cells that are necessary for defining and mineralizing the enthesis (Figure 3). Understanding how cells build a functional attachment between tendon and bone provides a roadmap for improved healing and for development of tissue engineered replacements.

Figure 3: The fate of hedgehog-active cells at the enthesis is shown in green, labelled at 7 days after birth (P7, left) and 52 days after birth (P52, right) in mice. These cells build the enthesis, turning off hedgehog activation with maturity (P56). Scale = 100 μm, t: tendon and b: bone.

2.3 Application to regenerative medicine

Materials can be synthesized that mimic the design of the healthy enthesis, either directly or through appropriately-stimulated cells [26, 42-45]. We developed nanofiber scaffolds with spatial gradients in mineral, mimicking natural gradients. These compositional gradients resulted in a graded mechanical response (Figure 4) and a spatially graded cellular response. These cell-based materials are currently being optimized for in vivo use.

Figure 4: (A) Testing of scaffolds with spatial gradients in mineral were performed from slack conditions, and conducted with a strain rate of 0.4 %/sec to achieve quasi-static loading conditions. (B) Locations were selected from the grip-to-grip stress-strain curve. The images were then analysed to demonstrate the effect of mineral content on the strain fields and mechanical properties. (C) Local strain fields were calculated directly. The first principal strain is shown using a heat map. (D) The relationship between modulus and mineral content was approximately linear, with the slope representing the stiffening effect of the mineral (R: Pearson's correlation coefficient).

2.4 Improving tendon-to-bone healing

Healing of tendon to bone does not reproduce the structural or compositional features of the healthy enthesis (Figure 5) [46-49]. This results in a mechanically inferior attachment that is prone to rupture. Healing can be improved through the implementation of design criteria from the uninjured attachment (e.g., through surgical manipulation), application of the roadmap defined from developmental biology studies (e.g., through the application of growth factor or cell-based therapies), or application of tissue engineered scaffolds.

Figure 5: The functionally graded transition between tendon and bone is not regenerated during the healing process (healthy attachment is shown on the left, healing attachment is shown on the right; hematoxylin- and eosin-stained images are shown under bright field in the top row and under polarized light in the bottom row).

3 CONCLUSIONS

The four research themes described above inform each other and are expected to lead to clinical therapies for tendon-to-bone repair. Basic science studies will identify the critical features necessary for successful tendon-to-bone repair and inform translational studies on cell- and growth factor-based regeneration for rotator cuff repair and anterior cruciate ligament reconstruction. Of critical importance is recreation of the multiscale mechanical behavior derived from the hierarchical structures at the health tendon-to-bone attachment.

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